

Synthesis and thermal characterization of metaphosphatecopper(II/I) salt

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Abstract : A new inorganically template metaphosphate of Cu^{II/I} complex has been synthesized and characterized by different instruments such as DSC, FT-IR, X-RD, ICP-AES and TG-DTA. The thermal properties have been studied at high temperature from 303 to 723 K by Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC). The specific heat capacity of the system is measured in atmospheric O₂ at heating rate of 283 K min⁻¹. The specific heat capacity is found negative at high temperatures.

Keywords : DSC, negative specific heat capacity, metaphosphatecopper(II/I).

Introduction

The preparation and structural chemistry of a number of organically template metal phosphates are extensively studied for their potential applications in many fields in the past few decades¹. Some metal phosphites are reported for replacing metal phosphate². Many open-framework metal phosphites are synthesized like [C₂H₁₀N₂].[Co₃(HPO₃)₄]³. Narain prepared some copper(II) phosphate complexes⁴. A number of copper(II) phosphate compounds are known like BaCu₂(PO₄)₂⁵, α-Cu₂P₂O₇⁵, Cu₅(PO₄)₂(OH)₄⁶, α,β-NaCuPO₄⁷ and many of their structures are complex three-dimensional frameworks like Na₆Cu₉(PO₄)₈⁸. The substitution of P^{III} for P^V is observed by Harrison *et al.* In this case hydrogen phosphate group, [HPO₃]²⁻, which is used as a new basic building block led to diversity of novel structures in organically template metal phosphates⁹. The copper(II) phosphate like Na₂CuP₂O₇¹⁰ and Ba₂Cu(PO₄)₂¹¹ exhibited Cu-O-P-O-Cu bond interactions. The negative specific heat capacity is found by Swain for some phosphate complexes and methionine bridged metal complex at high temperature¹². Out of different approaches, one of the approach is based on the reduced partition function of the system defined as¹³,

$$Z = \frac{Z_{S+B}}{Z_B} \quad (1)$$

In the absence of a coupling between the system and its environment, Z equals the partition function of the system; the partition function can be used to define thermodynamic equilibrium quantities by means of the standard relations valid in the absence of a coupling between the system and its environment. S and B indicated for complex of system and heat bath respectively. Quantities related to the coupled system will be indicated by a subscript $S+B$. A second expression for the specific heat can be obtained as below¹³,

$$C = k_B \beta^2 \frac{\delta^2 \ln(z)}{\delta \beta^2} \quad (2)$$

where, $\beta = 1/k_B T$. k_B is the Boltzmann constant. In the absence of coupling between system and bath, this definition of specific heat also reduces to the usual definition.

However, using only metaphosphoric acid in the preparation of homo-metallic copper complex is not synthesized till now.

Here, I have explored cause of negative specific heat at high temperature using thermodynamic properties like studied by Swain¹² for cobalt and methionine bridged cobalt complexes and solution of theory proposed by Bandyopadhyay regarding negative specific heat. This complex can be used as heat resistance below room temperature and at high temperature above 686 K.

Results and discussion

X-Ray crystallography :

The X-RD spectrum of the complex is displayed in Fig. 1. The H...H bond length was found at 1.308 Å instead of 1.319 Å and made an angle of 72.141°¹². The S-H bond length was found at 1.373 Å and made an angle of 68.2°¹⁴. The bond length 1.515 Å was for P=O¹⁵ and made an angle of 61.09°. The 1.615 Å bond length was for P-O(-P) instead of 1.608 Å¹² and made an angle of 56.93°. The bond length of P-O was found at 1.718 Å and made an angle of 53.26°¹². The 1.906 Å bond length was for Cu^I-O instead of 1.894 Å¹⁶. This plane made an angle of 47.66°. The bond length 2.183 Å was for Cu-P and made an angle of 41.31°. This bond length is almost equal to Churchill *et al.*¹⁷. The Cu-S bond length was found at 2.430 Å instead of 2.38 Å¹⁸ and made an angle of 36.96°. The O-Na bond length was 2.687 Å instead of 2.65 Å as per Angeli *et al.*¹⁹ and made an angle of 33.31°. The Cu-O out-of-plane bond length was 2.891 Å which was for Cu^{II} complexes with ETO stereochemistry²⁰. This out-of-plane made an angle of 30.89°. The distance between two copper atoms was 2.984 Å instead of 2.991

Å²¹. From Churchill *et al.*, it is indicating that the two copper atoms have a tetrahedral coordination geometry while other two copper atoms are in trigonal-planar coordination sites. These copper atoms made an angle of 29.91°. The bond length of 3.128 Å was for P-O-P-O instead of 3.148 Å¹² and this plane made an angle of 28.50°. The Cu(S)₂-O bond length was 6.766 Å instead of 6.849 Å and made an angle of 12.91°. The bond length of H-S-Cu(O)-S-H was 9.506 Å instead of 9.300 Å and this plane made an angle of 9.50°. The P-O-Cu-P-O-P-O-Na bond length was 11.39 Å instead of 11.307 Å and made an angle of 7.81°.

FT-IR analysis :

The FT-IR spectrum of the complex is displayed in Fig. 2. Some works, Khan *et al.* in a study of phosphate glasses, suggested a combined effect of all constituents for explaining the broadening and shifting of the bands with formation of Cu-O-P-O units in the region 410–610 cm⁻¹²². This suggestion is consistent with the nano-crystalline model made of four phosphate tetrahedral. Firstly, the (PO₄)³⁻ band at 504 cm⁻¹ present in IR spectra of metaphosphoric acid of the bulk sample is replaced by

Fig. 1. X-RD spectrum of sample at room temperature.

Fig. 2. FT-IR spectrum of the complex.

much sharper band at 514 cm^{-1} . This seems to be due to both strong P-O and the weak Cu-O bands in the nanosample. The Cu-O is known to have a fundamental band at 620 cm^{-1} which is being replaced by the band at 618 cm^{-1} instead of 615 cm^{-1} ²³. The P-O-P ring frequency is observed at 712 cm^{-1} . The (P-O-P)_{as} vibration of BOs in the linkages was 888 cm^{-1} ²⁴. The band at 910 cm^{-1} can be assigned to P-O stretching band of the P-OH system. Barja and Afonso also attributed a band near to 910 cm^{-1} to the P-OH group²⁵. The band at 993 cm^{-1} assigned for PO_2 s-vibration. The band at 1062 cm^{-1} assigned for asymmetric stretching vibration of O-P-O¹². The stretching vibration of P=O found at 1246 cm^{-1} ²⁶. The bands at 993, 1062 and 1154 cm^{-1} were stretching vibration of P-O²⁷. The band at 1652 cm^{-1} was due to bending of water molecule²⁷. The broad band at 1652 cm^{-1} was due to crystal waters²⁸. The O-H stretching

frequency found at 3413 cm^{-1} instead of 3431 cm^{-1} at pH 7.00²⁹.

Elemental analysis :

The elemental analysis of the bulk product was also consistence with theoretical values. Anal. Calcd. for complex $\{\text{Cu}_{15}\text{P}_{16}\text{SO}_x\text{Na}_y\text{H}_z\}$ is Cu : $27.86 \pm 0.1\%$, P : $14.47 \pm 0.1\%$ and S : 0.935 ± 0.1 . Found Cu : $27.97 \pm 0.1\%$, P : $14.5 \pm 0.1\%$ and S : $0.935 \pm 0.1\%$.

TG-DTA analysis :

From TG analysis, the mass loss as temperature increased up to 699.59 K was 13.35% . At this temperature all light particles were removed such as Na and H. At this temperature maximum absorption of heat was occurred. The TG-DTA spectrum is figured in Fig. 3. From DTA spectrum, the reaction is found exothermic in nature.

Fig. 3. TG-DTA spectra of complex.

Differential scanning calorimeter :

Heating rate – 283 K/min :

At high temperature :

The DSC spectrum is figured in Fig. 4. In eq. (2), I assumed the removal particle to consist of harmonic oscillators and the coupling to be bi-linear in complex and removal coordinates. In order to know the appearance of negative specific heat (2), it was sufficient to consider a

Fig. 4. DSC spectra at 283 K/min from 303 to 723 K.

stylized minimal model where the remove particle consisted of only a single degree of freedom described by the Hamiltonian.

$$H_R = \frac{P^2}{2m} + \frac{f_R}{2} q^2 \quad (3)$$

where f_R denotes the spring constant. The complex governed by the Hamiltonian

$$H_C = \frac{P^2}{2M} + \frac{f_C}{2} Q^2 \quad (4)$$

In the case of free particle, oxidation (O_2) (spring constant $f_C = 0$) and of a harmonic oscillator ($f_C > 0$), the coupling Hamiltonian is given by

$$H_{CR} = f_R q Q + \frac{f_R}{2} Q^2 \quad (5)$$

The mass of a single remove particle oscillator was m . This removal particle coupled with complex having mass M , harmonically. In my analysis a free particle (O_2) was in contact with the single degree of freedom environment described by eqs. (3) and (5). Complex and removal particles are assumed to stay in thermal equilibrium with each other at the inverse temperature β . Hence, the density matrix of the total system is given by a Gibb's state.

$$\rho_{CR} = Z_{CR}^{-1} \exp [-\beta(H_C + H_R + H_{CR})] \quad (6)$$

where, $Z_{CR} = T_i \exp [-\beta(H_C + H_R + H_{CR})]$ denotes the partition function of the total system.

The partition function of the removal particle's degree of freedom is given by

$$Z_R = \frac{1}{2 \sin \left(\frac{\hbar\beta\omega_0}{2} \right)} \quad (7)$$

where,

$$\omega^2 = \left(\frac{f_R}{m} \right) \quad (8)$$

ω_0 was the frequency of remove particle oscillator. From eq. (2) the specific heat capacity of this removal particles are given below.

$$C_R = k_B g \left(\frac{\hbar\beta\omega_0}{2} \right) \quad (9)$$

where,

$$g(x) = \left(\frac{x}{\sin x} \right)^2 \quad (10)$$

In order to obtain a well-defined partition function for the free particle, I restricted its motion to a region of inside the system. The system is supposed to be sufficiently large such that the energy level spacing can be neglected in compared with the thermal energy $k_B T^{30}$. Under this condition the space of this system will turn out to be irrelevant in the sequel.

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The frequency of underdamped complex ($\zeta < 1$)

$$\omega = \omega_0 \{ \zeta \pm (\zeta^2 - 1)^{\frac{1}{2}} \}$$

ζ is called as damping ratio. In this case the complex loses energy along with removal particles and return to the thermally stable state.

The specific heat capacity of complex is given below

$$C_c = k_B g \left(\frac{\hbar \beta \omega}{2} \right)$$

The total heat capacity of the system is given below

$$C = C_C + C_R = -k_B g \left(\frac{\hbar \beta \omega}{2} \right) + k_B g \left(\frac{\hbar \beta \omega}{2} \right)$$

The polynomial equation for specific heat capacity, enthalpy and entropy derived from DSC is given below

$$Y\{ (C_p), (H_T - H_{303}), (S_T - S_{303}) \} = a_n T^n + a_{n-1} T^{n-1} \dots \dots \dots + a_2 T^2 + a_1 T + C$$

The values of $a_1, a_2, a_3 \dots a_n$ and C are given in Table 1.

The complex is heated at atmospheric oxygen at heat-

Table 1. Specific heat capacity, enthalpy and entropy of metaphosphate salt of copper(I/II) at high temperature

Sl. No.	Thermodynamic parameter	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	C	Temperature range
1.	Specific heat	3.0×10^{-4}	-4.0×10^{-7}	-	-	-3.84×10^{-2}	304.97-344.92
2.		7.78×10^{-2}	-2.0×10^{-4}	2.0×10^{-7}	-	-9.3748	345.42-378.82
3.		2.9×10^{-3}	-3.0×10^{-6}	-	-	-0.5979	379.33-395.93
4.		1.04×10^{-2}	-2.0×10^{-5}	2.0×10^{-8}	-	-1.4839	396.43-440.97
5.		3.0×10^{-4}	-5.0×10^{-7}	3.0×10^{-10}	-	-4.22×10^{-2}	441.47-532.97
6.		-3.0×10^{-5}	3.0×10^{-8}	-	-	7.3×10^{-3}	533.47-589.97
7.		8.0×10^{-5}	-7.0×10^{-8}	-	-	-2.47×10^{-2}	590.47-602.97
8.		7.4×10^{-3}	-1.0×10^{-5}	6.0×10^{-9}	-	-1.5268	603.47-612.97
9.		4.0×10^{-4}	-7.0×10^{-7}	4.0×10^{-10}	-	-6.72×10^{-2}	613.47-669
10.		-1.0×10^{-3}	7.0×10^{-7}	-	-	0.3386	669.5-698.59
11.		12.29	-2.6×10^{-2}	2.0×10^{-5}	-9.0×10^{-9}	2181.3	699.09-723.02
1.	Entropy	3.0×10^{-4}	-4.0×10^{-7}	-	-	-3.79×10^{-2}	304.97-344.92
2.		7.78×10^{-2}	-2.0×10^{-4}	2.0×10^{-7}	-	-9.3743	345.42-378.82
3.		2.9×10^{-3}	-3.0×10^{-6}	-	-	-5.97×10^{-1}	379.33-395.93
4.		1.04×10^{-2}	-2.0×10^{-5}	2.0×10^{-8}	-	-1.4834	396.43-440.97
5.		3.0×10^{-4}	-5.0×10^{-7}	3.0×10^{-10}	-	-4.17×10^{-2}	441.47-532.97
6.		2.92×10^{-2}	-8.0×10^{-5}	9.0×10^{-8}	-4.0×10^{-11}	-4.0809	533.47-589.97
7.		8.0×10^{-5}	-7.0×10^{-8}	-	-	-2.42×10^{-2}	590.47-602.97
8.		3.0×10^{-4}	-3.0×10^{-7}	-	-	-9.34×10^{-2}	603.47-612.97
9.		-1.0×10^{-4}	1.0×10^{-7}	-	-	4.5×10^{-2}	613.47-669
10.		-1.0×10^{-3}	7.0×10^{-7}	-	-	3.38×10^{-1}	669.5-698.59
11.		12.29	-2.6×10^{-2}	2.0×10^{-5}	-9.0×10^{-9}	-2181.3	699.09-723.02
1.	Enthalpy	9.8×10^{-2}	-2.0×10^{-4}	-	-	-14.54	304.97-344.92
2.		28.22	-7.8×10^{-2}	7.0×10^{-5}	-	-3402.1	345.42-378.82
3.		9.8×10^{-1}	-1.2×10^{-3}	-	-	-204.19	379.33-395.93
4.		4.052	-9.5×10^{-3}	7.0×10^{-6}	-	-578.04	396.43-440.97
5.		1.1×10^{-1}	-2.0×10^{-4}	2.0×10^{-7}	-	-18.26	441.47-532.97
6.		16.25	-4.3×10^{-2}	5.0×10^{-5}	-2.0×10^{-8}	-2275.5	533.47-589.97
7.		4.65×10^{-2}	-4.0×10^{-5}	-	-	-14.009	590.47-602.97
8.		1.9×10^{-1}	-2.0×10^{-4}	-	-	-57.72	603.47-612.97
9.		3.5×10^{-1}	-6.0×10^{-4}	4.0×10^{-7}	-	-66.73	613.47-669
10.		15.38	-2.3×10^{-2}	1.0×10^{-5}	-	-3429.6	669.5-698.59
11.		-38.16	5.2×10^{-2}	-2.0×10^{-5}	-	9222.3	699.09-723.02

ing rate of 283 K min⁻¹. The weight of complex should increase due to oxidation (addition of oxygen) but this increase in weight was less than that of weight loss due to high heating rate. So, the increase in weight is not detected during DSC measurements. After 669.5 K, the specific heat capacity found positive due to absorption of heat and there was no mass loss.

Experimental

Materials and synthesis :

In a typical synthesis for this compound 1 mole of CuSO₄.5H₂O and 1 mole of metaphosphoric acid (60% HPO₃ + 40% NaPO₃) were dissolved in 20 cc of double distilled water. Both solutions were mixed at room temperature and stirred under ambient conditions until homogeneous. The stirred solution was left for 120 h. The resulting solution was neutralized to pH 7 by addition of alkali (0.1 N NaOH). The neutralized solution was stirred for 6 h under ambient conditions. Then it was left for 120 h. The resulting product was filtered, washed and dried in desiccators. Highly purified, deionized water was used in all solutions. Second distillation was carried out from alkaline KMnO₄ using an all-glass distillation apparatus.

Experimental procedure :

An infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) spectrum was obtained using a Thermo-Nicolet avtar 370 of solid sample. Differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) measurements were performed on a Mettler Toledo, DSC 822 on 283 K/min under atmospheric condition. The X-ray crystallography measurement of powder sample was carried out using Bruker AXS D8 Advance. ICP-AES measurement was performed using Thermo Electron IRIS Intrepid II XSP DUO system for Cu and P determination as follows. The sample was dissolved in 5 ml HNO₃ and made up into 100 ml using HPLC grade water. FT-IR, DSC, XRD, TG-DTA and ICP-AES were performed at ST&IC, Cochin University of Science and Technology, Cochin.

To determine the crystal structure of powder copper complex X-ray diffraction, data are collected at room temperature with graphite-monochromated Mo K α radiation on an XPERT PRO diffractometer operating in $\omega/2\theta$ scan mode. The Thermo gravimetric analysis (TG) and Differential thermal analysis (DTA) studied for the complex was made Perkin-Elmer, Diamond TG/DTA ther-

mal analyser between 314.71 and 1262.36 K in N₂ atmosphere. The pH measurements were performed using a Nucleonix type DP 301 digital pH meter equipped with combination of glass – Ag/AgCl/Cl⁻ (3 mol dm⁻³ NaCl) electrode. It was calibrated with standard buffers of pH 4.0, 7.0 and 9.0 (Merck).

Conclusion

The metaphosphatecopper(II/I) synthesized and thermally characterized by differential scanning calorimeter at both low and high temperatures. At this temperature it found that the specific heat capacity was negative due to loss of mass at high temperature.

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